

PRESINMED

“Preserving the singularity of Mediterranean high-mountain biodiversity hotspots: a NbS approach”

Restoration Actions

WP2: Implement mitigation, adaptation and restoration measures for biodiversity and its ecological functions using NbS - **Task 2.2**

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1. Tasks 2.2.1 and 2.2.2: Irrigation system reclamation and monitoring the responses of the plant community to the water supply

Once we provide an extra supply of water, in order to obtain a permanently moisture soil during the summer, we will determine the response of the community to this supply, following an observational and experimental approach. The observational approach involves monitoring the responses of the plant community to the water supply and/or to the impact of livestock pressures.

1.1. Methodology proposal

- 1) **Experimental area** (see [Figure 1](#)): identify severely degraded pasturelands with bare soil and topsoil absent that will receive additional water supply. Ideally, the area should have between 300 and 400m², although it is possible to work with smaller areas. The additional water can be supplied to this experimental unvegetated area by means of a small ditch or a pipe, by flooding, or alternatively by sprinklers, in order to obtain a permanently moisture soil during the summer, simulating the conditions of a wet pastureland. In this irrigated area, we propose a minimum of 9 experimental plots of 2x2m divided into three sets of three plots each for: **passive restoration** (only irrigation); **active restoration**: seeding (seeding of native species), and **turf addition** (nursery-grown turf with native seeds).
- 2) **Control area** (see [Figure 1](#)): designate a natural wet meadow area in optimal conditions and as close as possible to the experimental plots that will act as a control and reference ecosystem for the restoration plots evaluation. We propose a paired design consisting of 9 plots of 2x2m: 3

of them acting as control for passive restoration, 3 for seeding and 3 for turf addition.

Figure 1. Proposed design for restoration experiments. 1) Natural wet meadow with the corresponding control plots: (passive restoration control/sowing plots control/turf addition plots control), with 3 replicates (2x2 m plot each); 2) Experimental (irrigated) plots: 3 treatments (passive restoration/sowing/turf addition) with 3 replicates (2x2 m plot each), all with continuous moisture supply. **VERY IMPORTANT:** We must establish blocks in order to control unknown sources of spatial variations (eg. soil moisture). Within each block, all treatments are applied (see “Sampling design recommendations for Statistical Analysis” of [Field Sampling Methods Manual](#)).

The objective is to assess the capacity of certain pioneer herbaceous plant species to initiate and enhance the process of ecological succession, in order to restore the wet meadow plant community and its ecosystem services (Nature-based Solution, NbS).

1.2. Ungulate exclusions

Livestock impact will be controlled by performing small exclosures (each with its corresponding paired control). Exclosures will consist of metallic cages of 1,5x1,5m, fixed to the ground with anchors. A minimum number of 3 exclosures, with their controls, shall be placed per meadow and sampling site (see Table 1 of [WP1 Manual of field sampling methods](#)). The exclosure plots would be placed at the beginning of the project, and the composition and abundance of the herbaceous plant community, as well as the canopy cover, soil respiration, humidity and temperature, would be monitored inside the herbivore exclosure plots and outside, in control plots.

Figure 2. Ungulate exclosure 1,5x1,5m plot placed in high mountain wet meadows.

The objective is to assess the role of herbivory (through consumption or trampling) as a biotic filter of the plant community, in order to conserve and restore the wet meadow plant community and its ecosystem services (Nature-based Solution, NbS).

2. Task 2.2.3: Test of new restoration techniques

Certain plant species have the ability to colonise bare soil and facilitate the process of ecological succession, allowing other species to establish themselves later. That is why we are going to plant these pioneer species first, as they facilitate succession in the experimental plots that receive water. We will monitor the plots seasonally (spring, summer, autumn) over the 2-3 years of the project to determine whether a spontaneous ecological succession process is taking place, with the incorporation of other plant species, following the introduction of the pioneer species we have planted.

- **Manual sowing** of a seed mixture of native species composed of grasses (e.g. *Nardus stricta*, *Festuca iberica* and *Agrostis nevadensis* for Sierra Nevada) and other key species (obtained from the composition of reference ecosystem). Before sowing, native seeds should be collected in closest grasslands (see seed collection protocol section). The seed mixture will be manually seeded in the fall (before the first snowfall) in the sowing plots, which will be previously conditioned with the addition of 50 litres of commercial substrate per plot. It is recommended to sterilize the substrate (e.g. by heating it in an oven at 80-82°C for 30-60 minutes) before applying it to the plots.
- **Nursery-grown native turf** in an existing nursery or one created for this purpose. The requirements for the nursery are basic: i) concrete flooring or plastic weed barrier to prevent weeds and rooting of the sowed species, and ii) an irrigation system (preferably micro-sprinklers). It is recommended that the nursery be located in the mountain area to prevent the proliferation of weeds and lowland species in the turf.

The turf will have the following **design**: ii) A base which will consist of an organic blanket made of biodegradable materials (e.g., jute mesh with coconut straw; see [Figure 3](#)). Commercial organic blankets are usually 2.40m wide and vary in length, so they fit well into the 2x2m plot,

providing a small buffer that prevents the edge effect, ii) A uniform layer of commercial sterilised (e.g. by heating it in an oven at 80-82°C for 30-60 minutes) substrate about 5cm thick will be placed on top of it, and the mixture of native seeds will be sown on top of that.

It is recommended to sow in the fall and keep the turf blanket in the nursery until a compact lawn-like forms that does not disintegrate when handled (presumably 15-18 months after installation).

Finally, native turf should be installed just after the snowmelting of the experimental area.

Figure 3. Detail of an organic blanket made of biodegradable materials (jute mesh filled with coconut fiber).

- **Seed collection protocol.** Following, we provide a detailed seven-step protocol for collecting and preparing seeds for the restoration experiment. The steps cover species selection, site selection, collection timing, harvesting, cleaning, quantification, and preservation.
 1. **Species Selection:** Prioritize the selection of a wide range of species, focusing on those that are most abundant or play a key ecological role in the reference ecosystem, using the reference ecosystem as a guide.
 2. **Site Selection:** Choose the nearest native grassland to the experimental site to minimize the introduction of non-desirable species, ensuring a more focused and effective restoration effort.
 3. **Collection Date:** Determine the optimal time for seed collection by monitoring the target species to identify when the seeds are mature but before dispersal, ensuring maximum viability.
 4. **Collection:** Collect each species separately from plots where a given species is abundant. Place the harvested seeds, along with any accompanying plant material, in labelled paper bags, including details like species name, collection date, site coordinates, and collector/s information.
 5. **Seed Cleaning:** Clean the collected seeds by removing seed coats, fruits, and other plant debris. If seed predators are present, such as snout beetles (i.e. Curculionidae), consider using a pyrethrin-based insecticide, which have been proven not to interfere with seed germination.
 6. **Seed Quantification:** To estimate the approximate number of seeds in the sample, weigh three sub-samples separately using a precision scale. Count the seeds under a binocular microscope if necessary and then extrapolate the average seed count to the total sample weight.
 7. **Seed Preservation:** For short-term storage, keep the cleaned and quantified seeds in paper bags at room temperature in a dry, cool place until they are sown in the field or nursery.

3. Tasks 2.2.2 and 2.2.3: Passive and active restoration of dry/snowbeds meadows

The abandonment of traditional mountain uses has led to the scrub encroachment of mountain pastures, which is a very common process, especially in temperate mountains (Pyrenees, Alps, etc.). Scrub encroachment has traditionally been seen as a factor that negatively affects both the diversity and cover of the grassland community and livestock farming itself. However, it is well known that in highly stressed environments, such as the high Mediterranean mountains, some woody species can facilitate the establishment of other subordinate species. **Our hypothesis is that the most abundant woody species in high Mediterranean mountains (e.g. *Juniperus communis* in Sierra Nevada) may favour the establishment of other plant species under their canopy and in their immediate surroundings, increasing community diversity.** Woody plants provide to many herbaceous species a microclimatic shelter (from extreme temperatures, wind, frost, etc.) and a protective barrier against herbivores. The perennial nature of woody plants also allows them to accumulate organic matter under their canopy, creating islands of fertility in the bare soils of high mountains. For these three reasons (microclimatic improvement, protection from herbivores and soil improvement), woody plants can act as nurse species for many other herbaceous species in the high Mediterranean mountains.

To assess the possible nucleating role of high mountain scrub, we propose to determine:

- 1) The diversity (taxonomic, phylogenetic, functional) of plant species (herbaceous and woody) that establish themselves under the protection of high mountain scrub (*Juniperus communis* in the case of Sierra Nevada).
- 2) The ability of scrub to improve the microclimate under its canopy compared to the open ground of the nearby grassland.

- 3) The ability of scrub to protect plants growing under its canopy from herbivores, compared to plants growing in clearings.
- 4) The ability of scrubland to create islands of fertility under its canopy, compared to open grassland.

The Objective is to determine the role of high mountain scrubs fostering the biodiversity and abundance of the grassland community as a Nature-based Solution (NbS).

Important note: temporal changes (occurring in recent decades) in high mountain scrub cover will be quantified by the UGR group in all mountains included in the PRESINMED project using Remote Sensing.

3.1. Nucleation sampling protocol

We will sample the composition and abundance of herbaceous species in 1x1m quadrats associated with juniper. We will sample 1 to 3 quadrats above the canopy of each juniper/other scrub species (depending on its size), and another 1 to 3 quadrats in the nearest grassland (paired design) located at least 5m from the juniper, which will serve as a control. In the case of juniper, a size gradient will be sampled to determine whether the facilitating role changes with the size of the shrub (from 1x1m in diameter for the smallest junipers to 25x25m for the largest junipers). In Sierra Nevada, junipers will be sampled along an altitudinal gradient (low altitude = 2,200m a.s.l. ; medium = 2,500m, and high = 2,800m) and exposure gradient (north and south). Ideally, 30 junipers (with their respective 30 controls) will be sampled per altitude and exposure.

4. Task 2.2.4. Active restoration of keystone species: applied nucleation for restoration

Our goal is to take advantage of the capacity of certain species of woody plants in high mountain scrubland (in the case of Sierra Nevada, juniper) to generate islands of diversity, accelerating the process of ecological succession in dry grasslands and snowbeds in high mountains. Applied nucleation is a Nature-based Solution that can be easily integrated within ecological restoration plans. The implementation of applied nucleation can have important advantages over traditional extensive plantation approaches. For example: (1) the planted area is substantially reduced, shortening the implementation time and lowering the economic costs (2) different species combinations can be used in different nuclei specifically fitted for different micro-environmental conditions, improving plantation success and increasing automatically the α and β diversity of the restored ecosystem; (3) spatial arrangements and nuclei sizes and shapes can be designed to fulfil different objectives, like improved ecological connectivity and control of erosion, or providing recreational, economic or cultural services.

4.1. Restoration protocol

We will implement the restoration of keystone species, such as juniper in Sierra Nevada, or other key species in other study sites (e.g. endemic and threatened grasses and forbs) through seeding or planting experiments in areas of high-mountain dry meadows/snows beds, inside and outside enclosure plots. Restoration actions will be performed “mimicking nature”, reproducing the natural seed dispersal pattern, sowing the seeds and planting the saplings in the most successful microhabitats for recruitment (eg. next to a rock). Once the junipers have been planted, the establishment of herbaceous plants under the canopy/immediate surroundings of the planted juniper will

be determined throughout the duration of the project, in comparison with the establishment of grassland in open soil.

5. Task 2.2.4. Active restoration of keystone species: restoration of ecological interactions in wet meadows

Ecological restoration must recover both species and their ecological interactions, from which ecological functions are derived. Quantifying ecological interactions is a central aspect of conservation and restoration ecology, as these interactions define the functional roles of species and their associated ecosystem services. Therefore, when planning the active restoration of communities, it is essential to take into account the ecological interactions we also want to restore—particularly the positive interactions that provide stability and resilience to the community (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal). These are the interactions that will provide the ecological functions that support the ecosystem services underpinning Nature-based Solutions (NbS).

The objectives are:

- 1) To assess the role of pollinators for reproductive success of key plant species in order to maintain and restore wet meadow plant biodiversity and its ecosystem services (Nature-based Solution).**
- 2) To assess the role of herbivores as seed dispersers of plant species in order to maintain and restore wet meadow plant biodiversity and its ecosystem services (Nature-based Solution).**

Using the existing design of excluded and control plots in wet meadows, we will determine how the presence of ungulate herbivores alters the network of ecological interactions between plants and animals in these systems in two possible ways: by impoverishing the plant community and by promoting the establishment of invasive exotic plant species.

To assess the possible effects of herbivores on pollination networks, we propose to determine:

1. The diversity and relative abundance of native and invasive plant species. At least once a year, a survey will be conducted in each plot, recording the number of open flowers from each group, and categorizing them as wind-pollinated or insect-pollinated.
2. The taxonomic and functional diversity, as well as the relative abundance, of insects on the flowers of each of these two plant groups—both in control plots and in plots where ungulates are excluded. These pollinator samplings will be carried out at least once a year, preferably twice.
3. To assess the direct role of ungulates in the establishment of invasive species, we will collect ungulate excrements and determine the presence and viability of seeds, as well as whether they are native or exotic.

The objective is to determine the effect of livestock impact on the architecture of the pollination network, both directly—by modifying the availability of resources—and indirectly—by facilitating the entry of highly attractive invasive plant species.

5.1. Ecological interaction sampling protocol

As a first step, we will identify the plant species present in each plot (an activity already carried out in previous tasks), and categorize them as wind-pollinated, insect-pollinated, or self-pollinated. Also adding the presence or absence of clonal growth. This classification will be based on existing literature and the floral structure and plant architecture. Since we suspect this information may be lacking for many species in our study area, this step will be accompanied by field studies.

Next, we will identify the colonizing plant species. Some of these, such as *Carduus* or *Eryngium*, are highly attractive to insects, making them of particular interest. After identifying the plant species, we will record insect activity and abundance on the flowers. We will try to identify the insect species in the field, at least to morphospecies and functional group level.

To study the introduction of exotic and native-colonizer species into wet meadows via ungulates, we will collect fresh excrements in plots adjacent to the study plots. We will weigh the excrements and place them in trays for germination to determine which plant species emerge. We will try to identify the plant species at the seedling stage, and when this is not possible, we will let them grow for later identification.